

THE CRITICAL DISTANCE CONCEPT TO DESIGN NOTCHED 3D-PRINTED METALS AGAINST UNIAXIAL/MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE

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As far as notched components are concerned, the term “Theory of Critical Distances” (TCD) encompasses a set of design methodologies that employ a material length scale parameter to post-process the local linear-elastic stress fields damaging the material in the vicinity of the crack initiation points. This paper aims to review the ways the linear-elastic TCD is recommended to be applied to predict the fatigue strength of notched components fabricated from 3D-printed metals. To this end, the accuracy and reliability of the TCD in estimating fatigue strength of additively manufactured (AM) materials are assessed against a large dataset of experimental results. This dataset was generated by testing under both uniaxial and bi-axial cyclic loading AM specimens containing geometrical features of different sharpness. Through a systematic reanalysis, it becomes evident that TCD demonstrates high accuracy, with estimates predominantly falling within the calibration scatter bands of the parent material. This outcome holds significant relevance as it underscores the effectiveness of the linear-elastic TCD in successfully designing against fatigue loading notched components of AM metals, with this being achieved by directly processing the results from standard linear-elastic Finite Element (FE) models.

Keywords: Metal fatigue, Additive manufacturing, Critical distance, Critical plane.

INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing (AM) enables the production of objects from finely powdered or wired metal that is melted using either a laser or an electron beam. While conventional technologies offer a wide array of metals for fabrication, the selection of metallic materials suitable for effective AM is comparatively limited. Common metals suitable for AM include Ti-based and Ni-based alloys, various grades of stainless steel, and specific aluminium alloys.

Among the various AM technologies available, the Direct Metal Laser Sintering (DMLS) process stands out as the most widely adopted solution, particularly in the biomedical and aerospace engineering sectors (Chan et al. [1], Herzog et al. [2]).

In this manufacturing context, titanium alloy Ti6Al4V is particularly relevant due to its relatively high mechanical properties and low density, providing a favourable strength-to-weight ratio, making it suitable for applications requiring lightweight components (Qiu et al. [3]). However, experimental evidence highlights that AM Ti6Al4V components exhibit optimal mechanical behaviour when

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subjected to specific post-manufacturing processes, such as heat treatments. While these processes enhance mechanical response, especially fatigue performance, they also inevitably raise overall fabrication costs.

AISI 316L is certainly another metallic material that is widely used in industry to additively manufacture structural components. Recognised for its corrosion resistance and high-temperature performance, AISI 316L has gained prominence in various applications, including those requiring intricate designs and complex geometries. Despite its widespread use, modelling the fatigue behaviour of 3D-printed AISI 316L remains a critical aspect to ensure the structural reliability and longevity of components (Werner et al. [4], Cancli et al. [5]).

A significant advantage of AM is its ability to fabricate objects with complex shapes, achieving high accuracy in both form and dimensions. However, from a structural integrity perspective, the incorporation of intricate geometrical features in 3D-printed components can lead to localised stress concentration phenomena, markedly reducing the overall strength of the components themselves (Razavi et al. [6]). Consequently, precise and straightforward design techniques are essential for accurately assessing the fatigue performance of 3D-printed materials. In this context, a review of the current state of the art indicates that the Theory of Critical Distances (TCD) (Taylor [7], Susmel [8]) stands out as the most suitable candidate for designing notched AM components against fatigue loading. This is due to the following key reasons:

- irrespective of their shape and sharpness, the TCD effectively models the detrimental effect of notches;
- it takes into account the material morphology via suitable length scale parameters;
- its application does not necessitate the use of non-linear constitutive laws to model the mechanical behaviour of ductile metals;
- the TCD-based design is done by directly processing the results from conventional linear-elastic Finite Element (FE) models.

In this context, this conference paper reviews the work we have supervised in recent years (Wang et al. [9], Razavi et al. [10]) aiming at extending the use of the linear-elastic TCD to the structural assessment of 3D-printed notched metals subjected to both uniaxial and multiaxial fatigue loading.

THE THEORY OF CRITICAL DISTANCES IN BRIEF

When stress concentrators undergo Mode I fatigue loading, the TCD postulates that fracture occurs as soon as a critical distance-based effective stress $\Delta\sigma_{eff}$ becomes larger than the plain material fatigue limit, $\Delta\sigma_0$ [7]. In other words, a notched component is in uniaxial fatigue limit conditions when $\Delta\sigma_{eff} \leq \Delta\sigma_0$.

As far as the TCD is concerned, the necessary stress analysis can be performed directly using a straightforward linear-elastic constitutive law to model the material mechanical behaviour. This remains valid regardless of the degree of ductility exhibited by the metal under consideration (Susmel and Taylor [11]).

The aforementioned considerations highlight that the use of the TCD to design against high-cycle fatigue materials containing stress concentrators of all kinds involves a bi-parametric post-processing of the linear-elastic stress fields around the crack/notch tips. The two essential material parameters

for this process are the material characteristic length, L , and the plain material fatigue limit, $\Delta\sigma_0$, where L can be estimated as follows (El Haddad et al. [12]):

$$L = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(\frac{\Delta K_{th}}{\Delta\sigma_0} \right)^2 \tag{1}$$

In definition (1) ΔK_{th} is the range of the threshold value of the stress intensity factor.

Once L is determined through experiments, the TCD allows for the calculation of the effective stress ($\Delta\sigma_{eff}$) using either the Point Method, the Line Method, or the Area Method, i.e. [7]:

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \Delta\sigma_y \left(\theta = 0, r = \frac{L}{2} \right) \text{ – Point Method} \tag{2}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \frac{1}{2L} \int_0^{2L} \Delta\sigma_y(\theta = 0, r) dr \text{ – Line Method} \tag{3}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \frac{4}{\pi L^2} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^L \Delta\sigma_y(\theta, r) \cdot r \cdot dr \cdot d\theta \text{ – Area Method} \tag{4}$$

The adopted symbols and the meaning of $\Delta\sigma_{eff}$ determined according to definitions (2) to (4) are explained in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1 Notched component subjected to uniaxial fatigue loading (a); the TCD applied according to the Point (b), Line (c) and Area Method (d).

The TCD can be extended to the finite life regime by assuming that the critical distance varies as the number of cycles to failure decreases, i.e. [11]:

$$L_M(N_f) = A \cdot N_f^B \tag{5}$$

In this definition – Eq. (5), A and B represent material constants that can be determined through a series of appropriate fatigue experiments. It is important to note that, for a specific material, the

values of constants A and B are seen to vary with the load ratio. However, for a given material and a given load ratio, these values remain the same regardless of changes in the profile and sharpness of the notch being designed. The detailed procedure for determining constants A and B in power law (5) will be thoroughly discussed at the end of this section.

Once the relationship between L_M and N_f is obtained from experiments, the TCD can be applied directly by simply rewriting Eqs (2) to (4) as follows (Susmel [11], Susmel [13]):

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \Delta\sigma_y \left(\theta = 0, r = \frac{L_M(N_f)}{2} \right) \text{ - Point Method} \tag{6}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \frac{1}{2L} \int_0^{2L_M(N_f)} \Delta\sigma_y(\theta = 0, r) dr \text{ - Line Method} \tag{7}$$

$$\Delta\sigma_{eff} = \frac{4}{\pi L_M^2(N_f)} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \int_0^{L_M(N_f)} \Delta\sigma_y(\theta, r) \cdot r \cdot dr \cdot d\theta \text{ - Area Method} \tag{8}$$

After determining $\Delta\sigma_{eff}$ through one of the above definitions, the estimation of the number of cycles to failure can be directly derived from the SN curve that quantifies the fatigue strength of the un-notched material under consideration [11]:

$$N_f = N_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta\sigma_0}{\Delta\sigma_{eff}} \right)^k \tag{9}$$

Here, $\Delta\sigma_0$ represents the plain material endurance limit extrapolated at N_0 cycles to failure, and k is the negative inverse slope of the plain material fatigue curve.

FIGURE 2 Determination of the L_M vs. N_f relationship from two different fatigue curves.

The formulation of the TCD as discussed above implies that the number of cycles to failure can be estimated by employing a suitable recursive numerical procedure. This necessity arises because, in the design problem, N_f is the unknown variable, but it is also required to estimate the critical distance value from Eq. (5).

Regarding the calibration of the L_M vs. N_f relationship as defined in Eq. (5), obtaining constants A and B requires two distinct pieces of experimental information. For example, these could be directly derived from the critical distance determined under static loading and the critical distance estimated in the high-cycle fatigue regime [11]. Unfortunately, this approach is not straightforward in practice due to two main reasons [11, 12]: (i) the stress-based approach lacks accuracy in modelling materials failing in the low-cycle fatigue regime, and (ii) the position of the knee point defining the endurance limit in the high-cycle fatigue regime varies with changes in the profile and sharpness of the calibration notches being tested.

These limitations can be overcome by determining constants A and B in Eq. (5) from the un-notched material fatigue curve and another fatigue curve obtained by testing specimens containing a notch with a known profile and sharpness [11, 12]. This approach is illustrated in the SN diagram shown in Fig. 2. According to the Point Method, given a reference number of cycles to failure, N_f^* , it is straightforward to determine the distance from the notch tip, $L_M(N_f^*)/2$, at which $\Delta\sigma_y$ equals the value of the stress range that must be applied to the plain material to break it at N_f^* cycles to failure (Fig. 2). Following this procedure, the critical distance value can then be determined for all N_f values from the low- to the high-cycle fatigue regime, allowing constants A and B to be unambiguously established. This straightforward strategy will be employed in the next sections to assess whether the linear-elastic Theory of Critical Distances is also successful in estimating the fatigue lifetime of notched AM metals.

ACCURACY OF THE TCD IN THE PRESENCE OF UNIAXIAL FATIGUE LOADING

In order to check the accuracy of the TCD in predicting uniaxial fatigue strength of notched AM metals, a comprehensive experimental investigation was conducted, involving the testing of flat samples of AM Ti6Al4V containing three different geometrical features [10]. The sharply V-notched samples had a gross width (w_g) of 12.1 mm, a net width (w_n) of 4.7 mm, a notch root radius (r_n) of 0.4 mm, and a notch opening angle of 35°. The associated net tensile stress concentration factor (K_t) was equal to 3.4. The intermediate U-notched specimens had $w_g=12.1$ mm, $w_n=5.8$ mm, and $r_n=0.7$ mm ($K_t=2.9$). The bluntly U-notched samples had $w_g=12.1$ mm, $w_n=6.0$ mm, and $r_n=1.5$ mm ($K_t=2.1$).

The parent material employed for this experimental investigation was AM Ti6Al4V, and the specimens were fabricated using the DMLS technology through 3D printer EOS M280 with a maximum laser power of 400 W. Throughout manufacturing, the laser power was set at 280 W, the scan speed at 1200 mm/sec, and the hatch distance at 0.140 mm. All specimens underwent fatigue testing in the as-manufactured condition.

Both the plain and notched specimens underwent testing under sinusoidal axial loading. Due to the small net cross-sectional area of the specimens, fatigue tests were conducted until the samples completely fractured. The experiments were all performed at a frequency of 10 Hz. The nominal load ratio, R , was taken not only equal to -1 but also to 0.1. Run-out tests were stopped at 2×10^6 cycles to failure. All tests were conducted at room temperature.

To apply the TCD for post-processing the notch fatigue results being generated, linear-elastic local stresses were determined using FE software ANSYS®. The pertinent linear-elastic stress fields

in the notched specimens were calculated by solving bi-dimensional FE models built up by using 4-node structural plane elements (plane 182). Following the fundamental assumption upon which the TCD formulation relies, numerical solutions were computed under the assumption that the investigated AM titanium alloy behaves as a linear-elastic, homogeneous, and isotropic material. To ensure the necessary stress fields were accurately determined, the mesh density around the notch tips was progressively increased until convergence was achieved.

As depicted in the calibration strategy shown in Fig. 2, constants A and B in Eq. (5) for the assessed AM material were determined for a probability of survival, P_S , equal to 50% using both the experimental plain fatigue curve and the fatigue curve obtained by testing the sharply notched specimens. This approach was employed to establish the L_M vs. N_f relationship for both the $R=-1$ case and the $R=0.1$ case.

FIGURE 3 L_M vs. N_f relationship from AM Ti6Al4V (a); accuracy of the Point (b), Line (c) and Area Method (d) in estimating the fatigue lifetime of the tested specimens of AM Ti6Al4V.

By post-processing the local linear-elastic stress field determined numerically for the sharply notched specimens, the procedure outlined in Fig. 2, utilizing the two calibration fatigue curves mentioned earlier, yielded the results presented in the chart of Fig. 3a. This chart indicates a minimal variation of L with N_f . Consequently, it was hypothesized that the critical distance could be considered constant and averaged over the fatigue lifetime interval of interest. This approach was

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applied for both the $R=-1$ case and the $R=0.1$ case, resulting in an average critical distance value of approximately 0.6 mm. Thus, it was assumed that, for the specific AM material under investigation, constant B in Eq (5) could consistently be considered zero, leading to the critical distance value, L_M , invariably equal to 0.6 mm.

This constant critical distance value was then used to post-process the generated experimental results according to the Point, Line, and Area Method. The obtained results are summarised in the experimental, N_f , vs. estimated, N_{fe} , diagrams in Figs 3b to 3d, where the data are categorized based on the sharpness of the notch. These charts reveal that predictions using the Line Method (Fig. 3c) were uniformly distributed within the parent material scatter band. In contrast, the use of both the Point Method (Fig. 3b) and the Area Method (Fig. 3d) resulted in estimates characterized by a slight degree of conservatism, however mainly within the target error band.

THE THEORY OF CRITICAL DISTANCES APPLIED ALONG WITH THE MODIFIED WÖHLER CURVE METHOD

In order to use the TCD to perform the fatigue assessment in the presence of multiaxial fatigue loading, it has to be applied along with a suitable multiaxial fatigue criterion. Based on our previous experience (Susmel and Taylor [14]), the highest level of accuracy is obtained by applying the TCD along with the critical plane concept formalised in the form of the Modified Wöhler Curve Method (MWCM).

The MWCM is a two-parameter multiaxial fatigue criterion assuming that the material plane used to estimate fatigue damage under multiaxial cyclic loading is the one undergoing the maximum shear stress amplitude. This assumption stems from empirical evidence suggesting that the probability of crack initiation is highest on those planes experiencing the maximum shear (Kanazawa et al. [15]).

The application of the MWCM involves calculating the maximum shear stress amplitude, τ_a , as well as the amplitude, $\sigma_{n,a}$, and mean value, $\sigma_{n,m}$, of the normal stress relative to the critical plane. The fatigue damage model underlying the MWCM accounts for the effects of these three stress components through the critical plane stress ratio (Susmel [13], Susmel [16]):

$$\rho_{eff} = \frac{m \cdot \sigma_{n,m} + \sigma_{n,a}}{\tau_a} \quad (10)$$

Here, m represents the mean stress sensitivity index, a material constant defining the portion of mean stress normal to the critical plane contributing to the propagation process by opening the micro/meso cracks. A crucial aspect of this stress ratio is that it is capable of taking into account both the presence of superimposed static stresses and the degree of multiaxiality/non-proportionality of the applied load history [13, 16]. Building on these considerations, during the development of the MWCM we hypothesized that, for a given material, fatigue damage should be the same irrespective of the complexity of the applied nominal loading path, as long as the assumed crack initiation point experiences the same values of both ρ_{eff} and τ_a .

The MWCM estimates fatigue lifetime under multiaxial cyclic loading from modified Wöhler curves that are function of stress ratio ρ_{eff} . In particular, by assuming that both the inverse slope of the modified Wöhler curves, $k:(\rho_{eff})$, and the reference shear stresses, $\tau_{A,Ref}(\rho_{eff})$, at N_0 cycles to failure are linear functions of the ρ_{eff} ratio, N_f under multiaxial fatigue loading can be calculated as follows (Lazzarin and Susmel [17]):

$$N_{f,e} = N_0 \left[\frac{\tau_{A,Ref}(\rho_{eff})}{\tau_a} \right]^{k_\tau(\rho_{eff})} \quad (11)$$

where [13]:

$$k_\tau(\rho_{eff}) = (k - k_\tau) \cdot \rho_{eff} + k_\tau \quad (12)$$

$$\tau_{A,Ref}(\rho_{eff}) = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{2} - \tau_0 \right) \cdot \rho_{eff} + \tau_0 \quad (13)$$

In relationships (3) and (4), k and σ_0 are the slope and the stress amplitude (endurance limit) extrapolated at N_0 cycles to failure characterising the fully-reversed uniaxial fatigue curve. Similarly, constants k_τ and τ_0 are the corresponding quantities associated with the fully-reversed torsional fatigue curve.

The MWCM can be used along with the TCD (formalised in the form of the Point Method) for estimating the finite life of mechanical components experiencing multiaxial cyclic loading and stress concentration phenomena. This design methodology assumes that the critical distance, L_M , used to evaluate fatigue damage in the medium-cycle multiaxial fatigue regime is a function of the number of cycles to failure, N_f – see Eq. (5) (Susmel [13], Susmel and Taylor [18]). In essence, the MWCM is applied by directly post-processing the linear-elastic stress state damaging a material point whose distance, $L_M(N_f)/2$, from the notch tip increasing as N_f decreases. According to the main feature of the TCD, the L_M vs. N_f relationship is assumed to be a material property to be determined experimentally. This hypothesis significantly simplifies the fatigue assessment problem since, for a given material, the same critical length can be used to estimate multiaxial fatigue damage independently of the considered geometrical feature.

ACCURACY OF THE TCD IN THE PRESENCE OF MULTIAXIAL FATIGUE LOADING

To assess the accuracy of the MWCM-based TCD in estimating multiaxial fatigue strength of AM notched metals, a comprehensive experimental investigation was carried out by testing notched cylindrical samples of AM AISI 316L [9]. These specimens had gross diameter equal to 12 mm and net diameter of 8 mm. Three different geometrical configurations were investigated, that is:

- sharply V-notched samples with a root radius, r_n , equal to 0.07 mm, resulting in a net stress concentration factor of 7.2 under axial loading (K_t) and of 3.1 under torsion (K_H);
- intermediate U-notched specimens with $r_n=2$ mm ($K_t=1.8$, $K_H=1.3$);
- bluntly U-notched cylindrical bars with $r_n=5$ mm ($K_t=1.4$, $K_H=1.1$).

The 316L stainless steel specimens utilised in this study were produced using the Selective Laser Melting (SLM) technology. The parent material underwent 3D-printing with laser power set at 450W, scan speed ranging from 1500-2000 mm/s, and scan pitch set to 0.05 mm. The final shapes of the specimens were created from rods that were initially additively manufactured in a flat orientation on the build plate. Subsequently, the 3D-printed rods underwent annealing before being machined with a conventional lathe. The post-AM heat-treatment involved setting the temperature at 490 °C and maintaining it for 6 hours, followed by cooling using argon.

The above specimens were tested under combined tension and torsion with zero ($R=-1$) and non-zero mean stress ($R=0$), with this being done by exploring both in-phase (IPh) and 90° out-of-phase (OoPh) scenarios.

The plain fatigue curve under fully-reversed uniaxial loading had a negative inverse slope of 15.3, with a reference stress amplitude of 249 MPa at 2×10^6 cycles to failure. Conversely, the fully-reversed plain torsional fatigue curve had a slope of 32.7, with a reference shear stress amplitude of 216.1 MPa at 2×10^6 cycles to failure. The mean stress sensitivity index, m , was directly derived from the plain uniaxial fatigue curve obtained under $R=0$ and was determined to be 0.53 [9].

FIGURE 4 Accuracy of the TCD applied along with the MWCM in estimating the multiaxial fatigue lifetime of sharply notched cylindrical specimens of AM AISI 316L [9].

FIGURE 5 Accuracy of the TCD applied along with the MWCM in estimating the multiaxial fatigue lifetime of intermediate U-notched cylindrical specimens of AM AISI 316L [9].

After calibrating the MWCM and validating its accuracy against data obtained from testing plain samples, the subsequent step involved analysing the results from notched specimens. The linear-elastic stress fields in the notch tip regions, essential for applying the TCD in the form of the Point Method, were determined using commercial software ANSYS®. This was achieved by solving axisymmetric FE models, with a gradual refinement of the mesh density until convergence was achieved.

Initially, the solutions from the linear-elastic FE analyses were employed to estimate the critical distance. In particular, L_M , Eq. (5), was directly estimated following the procedure outlined in Fig. 2. This involved post-processing the fully-reversed plain fatigue curve and the fully-reversed uniaxial fatigue curve generated by testing the sharply notched specimens (i.e., $r_n=0.07$ mm). This straightforward approach yielded a value for the high-cycle fatigue critical distance invariably equal to 0.44 mm [9].

FIGURE 6 Accuracy of the TCD applied along with the MWCM in estimating the multiaxial fatigue lifetime of bluntly notched cylindrical specimens of AM AISI 316L [9].

Accordingly, as postulated by the Point Method, the necessary linear-elastic stress states were computed at a distance from the notch tip equal to $L_M/2=0.22$ mm. These time-variable stress states were then post-processed to determine τ_a , $\sigma_{n,a}$, $\sigma_{n,m}$, and ρ_{eff} . The modified Wöhler diagrams reported in Figs 4 to 6 confirm that the use of the TCD applied along with the MWCM led to estimates characterized by a satisfactory level of accuracy. Only the experimental results obtained in the low-cycle fatigue regime from testing sharply notched specimens under 90° out-of-phase loading with $R=0$ (Fig. 4) are observed to be slightly on the non-conservative side. However, in practical scenarios, this could be easily compensated for by using appropriate design safety factors.

CONCLUSIONS

The TCD demonstrates its effectiveness in predicting the fatigue life of notched AM components under both uniaxial and multiaxial fatigue loading. This satisfactory level of accuracy is consistently achieved irrespective of the tested geometrical features and the profile of the loading path under

investigation. These promising outcomes strongly endorse the TCD as a valuable tool, enabling the design of notched 3D-printed metallic components against uniaxial/multiaxial fatigue while consistently ensuring a sufficient level of safety.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

A, B	material fatigue constants in the L_M vs. N_f relationship
k	negative inverse slope of the fully-reversed uniaxial fatigue curve
k_τ	negative inverse slope of the fully-reversed torsional fatigue curve
$k_\tau(\rho_{eff})$	negative inverse slope of the modified Wöhler curve
K_t	net stress concentration factor under tension
K_{tt}	net stress concentration factor under torsion
L	critical distance in the high-cycle fatigue regime
L_M	critical distance in the finite life regime
m	mean stress sensitivity index
N_0	reference number of cycles to failure
N_f	experimental number of cycles to failure
N_{fe}	estimated number of cycles to failure
P_S	probability of survival
R	stress ratio
r, θ	polar coordinates
r_n	notch root radius
w_g	gross width
w_n	net width
ΔK_{th}	threshold value of the stress intensity factor range
$\Delta\sigma_{eff}$	range of the linear-elastic effective stress
$\Delta\sigma_{nom}$	range of the nominal stress
$\Delta\sigma_y$	range of the linear-elastic stress
$\Delta\sigma_0$	range of the plain fatigue/endurance limit
ρ_{eff}	effective critical plane stress ratio
σ_0	fully-reversed uniaxial endurance limit at N_0 cycles to failure
$\sigma_{n,a}$	amplitude of the stress perpendicular to the critical plane
$\sigma_{n,m}$	mean stress perpendicular to the critical plane
τ_a	shear stress amplitude relative to the critical plane
τ_0	fully-reversed torsional endurance limit at N_0 cycles to failure
$\tau_{A,Ref}$	shear fatigue strength at N_0 cycles to failure

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) Chan, K.S., Koike, M., Mason, R.L., & Okabe, T., *Metall. Mater. Trans. A*, Vol. 44, No. 2, 2013, pp. 1010-1022.
- (2) Herzog, D., Seyda, V., Wycisk, E., & Emmelmann, C., *Acta Materialia*, Vol. 117, 2016, pp. 371-392.
- (3) Qiu, C., Yue, S., Adkins, N.J., Ward, M., Hassanin, H., Lee, P.D., Withers, P.J., & Attallah, M.M., *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 628, 2015, pp. 188-197.
- (4) Werner, T., Madia, M., Zerbst, U., *Procedia Structural Integrity*, Vol. 38, 2022, pp. 554-563.
- (5) Concli, F., Gerosa, R., Panzeri, D., Fraccaroli, L., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 177, 2023, 107931.

- (6) Razavi, N., Van Hooreweder, B., Berto, F., *Addit. Manuf.*, 2020, Vol. 36, 101426.
- (7) Taylor, D., *The Theory of Critical Distances: A new perspective in fracture mechanics*. Elsevier, Oxford, UK, 2007.
- (8) Susmel, L., *Eng. Fract. Mech.*, Vol. 75, No. 7, 2008, pp. 1706-1724.
- (9) Wang, Y., Wang, W., Susmel, L. *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 152, 2021, 106412
- (10) Razavi, N., Askes, H., Berto, F., Susmel, L., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol 167 (Part B), 2023, 107348.
- (11) Susmel, L., Taylor, D., *Fatigue Fract. Engng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 30, No. 7, 2007, pp. 567-581.
- (12) El Haddad, M. H., Topper, T. H., Smith, K. N., *Engng. Fract. Mech.*, Vol. 11, 1979, pp. 573–584.
- (13) Susmel, L., *Multiaxial Notch Fatigue: from nominal to local stress-strain quantities*. Woodhead-CRC-Elsevier, Cambridge, UK, 2009.
- (14) Susmel, L., Taylor, D., *SDHM Struct. Durab. Health Monit.*, Vol. 2, No. 2, 2006, pp. 91-108.
- (15) Kanazawa, K., Miller, K. J., Brown, M. W., *J. Eng. Mat. Techn. (Trans. ASME)*, Vol. 99, No. 3, 1977, pp. 222-228.
- (16) Susmel, L., *Fatigue Fract. Engng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 31, 2008, pp. 295-309.
- (17) Lazzarin, P., Susmel, L., *Fatigue Fract. Engng. Mater. Struct.*, Vol. 26, 2003, pp. 1171-1187.
- (18) Susmel L., Taylor, D., *Int. J. Fatigue*, Vol. 38, 2012, pp. 7-24, 2012.